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journal homepage: <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf>**MANAGEMENT OF STUDENT EDUCATION IN VOCATIONAL COLLEGES****Najmiddinov Dilshod Rafiddin ogli***Assistant of the Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan.***УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ОБУЧЕНИЕМ СТУДЕНТОВ В ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ КОЛЛЕДЖАХ****Наджмиддинов Дилшод Рафиддин оглы***Ассистент Джизакского филиала Национального университета Узбекистана.***KASB-HUNAR KOLLEJLARIDA TALABALAR TA'LIMINI BOSHQARISH****Najmiddinov Dilshod Rafiddin o'g'li***O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti Jizzax filiali assistenti.***abstract**

Vocational colleges are an important type of education in Uzbekistan. Vocational training is aimed at adapting to social needs and develops training plans based on the development of students' knowledge, ability, quality structure and technical application skills. Emphasizing both theoretical teaching and practical training, graduates acquire direct working skills. Currently, vocational education in Uzbekistan is in a period of significant change and development. In order to adapt more to the rapid development of society, many vocational colleges have implemented reforms in the student education management system with the aim of cultivating high-quality and qualified talents that meet the needs of social development, as well as ensuring high quality. New professional education services are being developed for the country and society.

аннотация

Профессиональные колледжи являются важным видом образования в Узбекистане. Профессиональное образование направлено на адаптацию к социальным потребностям и разрабатывает учебные планы на основе знаний, способностей, структуры качества и навыков технического применения учащихся. Делая упор как на теоретическое обучение, так и на практическое обучение, выпускники

получают навыки непосредственной работы. В настоящее время профессиональное образование в Узбекистане переживает важные изменения и развитие. Стремясь лучше адаптироваться к быстрому развитию общества, многие профессиональные колледжи провели реформы в системе управления обучением студентов, чтобы обеспечить более высокое качество и развитие высококачественных и квалифицированных талантов, отвечающих потребностям социального развития. Разрабатываются новые профессиональные образовательные услуги для страны и общества.

annotatsiya

Kasb-hunar kollejlari O'zbekistonda ta'limning muhim turi hisoblanadi. Kasb-hunar ta'limi ijtimoiy ehtiyojlarga moslashishga qaratilgan bo'lib, o'quvchilar bilimi, qobiliyati, sifat tuzilishi va texnik qo'llash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish asosida o'quv rejalarini ishlab chiqadi. Nazariy o'qitishga ham, amaliy mashg'ulotlarga ham urg'u berib, bitiruvchilar bevosita ishlash ko'nikmalariga ega bo'ladi. Hozirda O'zbekistonda kasb-hunar ta'limi muhim o'zgarish va rivojlanish davrida. Jamiyatning jadal rivojlanishiga ko'proq moslashish maqsadida ko'plab kasb-hunar kollejlari o'quvchilar ta'limini boshqarish tizimida ijtimoiy rivojlanish ehtiyojlariga javob beradigan

yuqori sifatli va malakali iste'dodlarni yetishtirish hamda yuqori sifatni ta'minlash maqsadida o'quvchilar ta'limini boshqarish tizimida islohotlarni amalga oshirdi. Mamlakat va jamiyat uchun yangi kasbiy ta'lim xizmatlari ishlab chiqilmoqda.

Keywords:

vocational colleges; educational management; model research.

Ключевые слова:

профессиональные колледжи, образовательный менеджмент, модельное исследование.

Kalit so'zlar:

Kasb-hunar kollejlari, ta'lim boshqaruvi, model tadqiqoti.

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Kirish

Kasb-hunar kollejlari o'quvchilar ta'limini boshqarishning yangi modellari bo'yicha olib borilayotgan izlanishlar doimiy ravishda rivojlanib bormoqda. Zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyasining uzluksiz rivojlanishi bilan ta'lim modellarini modernizatsiya qilish kasb-hunar kollejlari ta'limini boshqarishning asosiy elementiga aylandi. Biz hozirda talabalar ta'limini boshqarish samaradorligi va sifatini oshirish uchun bulutli hisoblash, katta ma'lumotlar va sun'iy intellekt kabi texnologiyalardan foydalanish usulini tadqiq qilmoqdamiz. Bunga talabalarning axborot tizimlari, onlayn kurslarni boshqarish va ta'lim ma'lumotlarini tahlil qilish bo'yicha tadqiqotlar kiradi. Shu bilan birga, kasb-hunar kolleji talabalari ta'limini boshqarish shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'limga ega va biz turli talabalarning ehtiyojlarini qondirish uchun shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'lim boshqaruviga erishish yo'llarini o'rganmoqdamiz. Bu talaba ma'lumotlariga asoslangan shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'lim yo'llari, shaxsiylashtirilgan o'quv resurslari bilan ta'minlash va aqlli repetitorlik tizimlarini rivojlantirishni o'z ichiga oladi.

Tahlil va natijalar

Kasb-hunar kollejlari martaba rivojlanishini qo'llab-quvvatlovchi omillar, jumladan, ularning ta'limni boshqarish metodlari nafaqat o'quv jihatlariga, balki o'quvchilarning kasbiy rivojlanishiga ham e'tiborni tobora ko'proq qaratmoqda. Talabalarning mehnat bozoriga yaxshiroq integratsiyalashuviga yordam berish uchun yaxshi martaba rejalashtirish va bandlikni qo'llab-quvvatlash usuli bo'yicha tadqiqotlar zarur. Kasb-hunar kolleji o'quvchilari ta'limini boshqarishda biz o'quvchilar ishtirokini va fikr-mulohazalar, qarorlar qabul qilish va ta'limni boshqarish jarayonini yaxshilash uchun so'rovlar, fikr-mulohazalar vositalari va ijtimoiy tarmoqlar orqali talabalarning fikrlarini to'plash. Kasb-hunar kollejlari o'quvchilar ta'limini boshqarish sifatini ta'minlash va baholash, shuningdek, ta'lim sifatini doimiy ravishda oshirishni ta'minlash maqsadida ta'limni boshqarish bo'yicha tadqiqotlarda

sifat kafolati va baholash jihatlarini ham o'z ichiga oladi. Shu bilan birga, u baholash standartlarini ishlab chiqish, o'qitishni baholash va o'qituvchilar malakasini oshirishni ham o'z ichiga oladi. Kasb-hunar kolleji talabalari ta'limini boshqarish bo'yicha transchegaraviy hamkorlik talabalar va jamiyat ehtiyojlarini yaxshiroq qondirish uchun ta'limni boshqarishni sanoat ehtiyojlari, hukumat siyosati va ijtimoiy muhit omillari bilan birlashtiradi. Ushbu maqolada kasb-hunar kollejlarda talabalar ta'limini boshqarish modelining joriy holati, mavjud muammolari va sabablari, yangi modelga erishish yo'llari o'rganiladi.

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib aytganda, asosiy fikrlar quyidagilardan iborat:

(1) Kasb-hunar kolleji talabalari ta'limini boshqarish texnologik rivojlanish va shaxsiylashtirilgan ehtiyojlar bilan bog'liq muammolarga duch kelmoqda va boshqaruv samaradorligi va ta'lim sifatini oshirish uchun zamonaviy usullarni qabul qilish kerak. Mavjud modelda mavjud muammolar qatoriga ta'lim resurslarining nomutanosib taqsimoti, o'quv rejasi va mehnat bozori o'rtasidagi uzilish, ta'lim sifatining beqarorligi, talabalarning bandligini ta'minlashning etarli darajada qo'llab-quvvatlanmasligi, ta'limni boshqarish jarayonlarining shaffof emasligi, texnologiya va ta'limni axborotlashtirish, ta'limni boshqarishda innovatsiyalarning etarli emasligi, talabalarning etarli darajada ishtirok etmasligi, sifatni baholash va nazorat qilish muammolari va boshqalar.

(2) Ushbu muammolarning sabablari orasida mablag'lar va resurslarning etishmasligi, siyosat va boshqaruv tizimi muammolari, mehnat bozoridan uzilish, eskirgan boshqaruv modellari, o'qituvchilar tarkibi, muammolar, talabalar ta'lim darajasidagi farqlar, ta'limni axborotlashtirish va texnologiya muammolari, ijtimoiy va madaniy omillar, yetarlicha nazorat va sifatni ta'minlash va boshqalar kiradi. Ta'limni boshqarishning yangi modelini amalga oshirish uchun kapital qo'yilmalarni ko'paytirish, sanoat tarmoqlari bilan hamkorlik qilish, ta'limni axborotlashtirish darajasini oshirish va shaxsiy ta'lim, o'qituvchilar sifatini yaxshilash, talabalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash va ish bilan ta'minlash xizmatlari, boshqaruv siyosati va jarayonlarini optimallashtirish, sifatni ta'minlash tizimini yaratish, innovatsiyalar va tadqiqotlarni rag'batlantirish, talaba ishtirok etish va siyosatni qo'llab-quvvatlash va boshqalarni amalga oshirish zarur.

(3) Ushbu amalga oshirish yo'llari muayyan sharoitlarga qarab moslashtirilishi kerak va hukumatlar, ta'lim muassasalari, o'qituvchilar va talabalar kasb-hunar kollejlarda talabalar ta'limini boshqarish sifati va samaradorligini oshirish, talabalar va jamiyat ehtiyojlarini qondirish uchun birgalikda ishlashi kerak. Umuman olganda, ushbu maqolada kasb-hunar kolleji o'quvchilarining ta'limini boshqarish bo'yicha chuqur tahlil va takliflar berilgan, kasb-hunar kolleji o'quvchilarining kasbiy

rivojlanishi va ijtimoiy integratsiyalashuviga ko'maklashish uchun zamonaviy, shaxsiylashtirilgan va kompleks boshqaruv usullari muhimligi ta'kidlangan.

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